

GLAUCOMA-PATHOGENESIS AND TREATMENT MODALITIES

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ABSTRACT

Glaucoma is the leading cause of irreversible blindness in the world. Due to its potential to cause permanent vision loss, it is important to understand how systemic conditions and their respective treatments can be associated with or increase the risk for developing glaucoma. The burden of irreversible vision loss from Glaucoma continues to rise. While the disease pathogenesis is not well understood, intraocular pressure (IOP) is the only modifiable risk factor identified to prevent glaucomatous vision loss. Medical management remains the first-line of treatment in most adult glaucoma and the evolution of medical therapy for glaucoma has followed an exponential curve. This review tracks the rapid development of new medications and drug delivery systems in the recent years.

INTRODUCTION

The global burden of irreversible vision loss from glaucoma continues to rise as the population ages. It was estimated to affect 64.3 million people aged 40–80 years in 2013, 76 million in 2020 with estimates increasing to 111.8 million in 2040. While the disease pathogenesis is not well understood, intraocular pressure (IOP) is the only modifiable risk factor identified to prevent glaucomatous vision loss. Medical management remains the first-line of treatment in most adult glaucoma which has been helped by the rapid development of unique agents in the last 50 years.^[1]

Pathophysiology

The retinal ganglion cells are neurons of the central nervous system that receive signals from the photoreceptors, process them, and transmit them in axons through the optic nerve to further centers in the brain. These axons run from the ganglion cell nuclei in the retina to the optic disc,^[2] and then together with the retinal vessels through the lamina cribrosa, a sieve-like structure composed of collagen. Behind the lamina cribrosa, the axons, surrounded by a myelin sheath, continue as the optic nerve. Elevated intraocular pressure, low perfusion pressure, and/or low cerebrospinal fluid pressure increase the gradient across the lamina cribrosa and cause papillary hypoperfusion, leading to structural changes and remodeling of the lamina cribrosa and to impaired axonal transport in the optic nerve fibers.^[3] In particular, the pores in the anterior region of the lamina cribrosa are elongated in open-angle glaucoma.^[4] The increasing loss of retinal ganglion cells leads to progressive impairment of the visual field, generally beginning in the mid-periphery

and then advancing until only a central or peripheral island of intact vision remains. Further functional disturbances include impaired contrast and color perception and difficulty in reading.^[5]

Symptoms

Acute angle closure can manifest itself with pain radiating from the eye, visual impairment, conjunctival hyperemia, and sometimes nausea and vomiting with a tense, rock-hard globe. This is an ophthalmological emergency that demands immediate treatment to prevent severe ocular damage and blindness. In contrast, open-angle glaucoma usually does not become symptomatic until it has reached an advanced stage. If visual field defects are present, they usually do not lie in the same part of the fields of the two eyes and are therefore well compensated by binocular vision. Thus, persons with open-angle glaucoma generally report no symptoms^[6] and many are completely unaware that they have the condition.^[7] One-third of patients already have the condition in an advanced or late stage in at least one eye at the time of diagnosis.^[8] Gramer et al. reported that 10–20% of patients were already unable to drive a vehicle at the time of presentation at the clinic because of binocular visual field defects.^[9]

Risk factors

The main risk factors for glaucoma are:

- Advanced age
- Elevated intraocular pressure
- High myopia
- A positive family history of glaucoma^[10]

Treatment

The only form of treatment that has been shown to be efficacious and is generally accepted for the prevention of glaucoma progression is reduction of the intraocular pressure, which is effective with a number needed to treat of.^[11] In patients with open-angle glaucoma, the intraocular pressure can be reduced with regularly applied eyedrops, laser therapy, and/or surgery.^[12] The goal is to achieve an individually set target pressure at which glaucoma is not expected to progress, and at which the lack of progression can be observed and documented. In each patient, the target pressure is

determined on the basis of the existing glaucomatous damage, the current intraocular pressure, the rate of structural and functional progression, other existing risk factors, and the potential side effects of treatment. These considerations determine the initial treatment measures. A pressure reduction rate in percent is no longer recommended as the sole treatment objective, because this takes no account of the absolute level of the initial intraocular pressure, which is an important component. Typical target pressures are < 21 mm Hg for early glaucoma, < 18 mm Hg for moderate glaucoma, and < 15 mm Hg for advanced glaucoma.^[13]

Clinically important pharmacological properties of antiglaucoma medications

<p>Inhibit aqueous inflow Beta blocker Concentration frequency Duration 1) Betaxolol 0.5% 2/day 12–18 hrs 2) Timolol 0.25%, 0.5% 1–2/day 12–24hrs 3) Levobunolol 0.25% 1–2/day 12–24 hrs Carbonic anhydrase inhibitors 1) Acetazolamide 250 mg tablets 1/2–4 tablets/day 6–12 hrs 2) Dorzolamide 2% 2–3/day 8–12 hrs 3) Brinzolamide 1% 2–3/day 8–12 hrs</p>
<p>Enhance conventional aqueous outflow (Via trabecular meshwork) Miotics 1) Pilocarpine 0.5%, 1%, 2%, 2–4/day 4–12 hrs 3%, 4%, 6% 2) Carbachol 1.5%, 3% 2–4/day 4–12 hrs Adrenergic drugs – May increase uveoscleral aqueous outflow as well 1) Dipivefrine 0.1% 2/day 12–18 hrs</p>
<p>Enhance uveoscleral (Unconventional) outflow PG Analogue Latanoprost 0.005% once daily 24–36 hours Travoprost 0.004% once daily 24–36 hours Bimatoprost 0.03% once daily 24–36 hours Unoprostone 0.15% 2/day 12–18 hours</p>

Clinically important pharmacological properties of antiglaucoma medications

<p>Dual action (Aqueous inflow Inhibition and Uveoscleral outflow enhancement) Concentration frequency Duration Alpha2 agonists 1) Brimonidine 0.2% 2–3/day 8–12 hours</p>
<p>Fixed combinations 1) Timolol/dorzolamide 0.5% / 2% 2/day 12 hours 2) Timolol/latanoprost 0.5% / 0.005% once daily 24 hours</p>

Rho kinase inhibitors

Rho A, Rho B and Rho C are a family of G proteins which are active when bound to guanosine triphosphate (GTP) and inactive when bound to guanosine diphosphate (GDP). The two Rho kinase isoforms (ROCK 1 and ROCK 2) are the effectors of the Rho family.^[14]

Rho kinase inhibitors increase aqueous outflow and decrease outflow resistance by increasing the ability of the Schlemm's canal endothelial cells to form pores. Another hypothesis is that Rho kinase inhibitors cause relaxation of the smooth muscle fibers in the trabecular meshwork and thereby increase outflow.^[15]

Ripasudil and netarsudil are the two commercially available formulations of Rho kinase inhibitors, both of which work on ROCK1 and ROCK 2 receptors. Ripasudil hydrochloride hydrate (Glanatec®) 0.4% reduced IOP by 2.6 mm of Hg at trough and 3.7 mm of Hg at peak in patients with primary open angle glaucoma (POAG) and ocular hypertension (OHT).^[6] The most commonly reported adverse events included conjunctival hyperemia (76%), blepharitis (21%).^[16]

Netarsudil (Rhopressa®) is a Rho kinase inhibitor and nor-epinephrine transporter inhibitor which decreases IOP by decreasing the outflow resistance. In addition, netarsudil caused reduction in aqueous humor production

in animal studies and decrease in episcleral venous pressure in animal and human studies.^[17]

Latanoprostene Bunod

Latanoprostene bunod 0.024% (LBN) is a unique nitric oxide (NO) donating Prostaglandin F2 alpha analogue. Latanoprost acid binds to the Prostaglandin F receptor and increases the uveoscleral outflow by matrix metalloproteinases-mediated remodelling of the extracellular matrix of the ciliary muscle.

In the eye, NO synthetases are present in the Schlemm's canal, trabecular meshwork, and ciliary body. NO causes vasodilation and smooth muscle cell relaxation. It decreases cell contractility and volume, thereby increasing trabecular outflow.^[18]

New glaucoma medications at various stages of development.^[19]

Glaucoma surgery

Surgery is indicated if nonsurgical treatment options are insufficient to lower the intraocular pressure to the target pressure, or cause intolerable side effects.

Minimally invasive, filtering, and non-filtering types of glaucoma surgery are available. For example, in one type of minimally invasive procedure a stent is placed in the canal of Schlemm to lower the outflow resistance through the trabecular meshwork. In general, this operation, which can be performed in combination with cataract surgery, does not lower the intraocular pressure enough, unless the glaucoma is only moderate in recent years, the surgical options have expanded markedly. Minimally invasive glaucoma surgery seems to have fewer side effects than a filtering procedure but also lowers the intraocular pressure by a lesser amount.^[20]

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